

National Open Access Monitor Advisory Group Meeting, 19th January 2024, 2pm

Agenda

1. **Minutes** of meeting 27th October 2023: <https://zenodo.org/records/10105024>
Approved 7th November 2023
2. **Matters Arising and Action Points:**

Outstanding Action Points from 27th October:

- a) **OpenAIRE:** *to provide screenshots showing how deliverables meet tender specifications (focusing on those detailed in the comments to the draft Inception Report).*
Action: OpenAIRE to provide for the next Advisory Group meeting.
 - b) **OpenAIRE:** *to deliver detailed documentation for RFOs and RPOs on what constitutes measures like findability, open access etc.*
Action: OpenAIRE to provide for the next Advisory Group meeting.
 - c) **OpenAIRE:** *to deliver detailed instructions for researchers on all aspects of the ORCID functionality: claiming, how this impacts these research outputs on the Monitor, logging in with ORCID and logging in with other credentials etc.*
Action: OpenAIRE to provide for the next Advisory Group meeting.
 - d) **Advisory Group:** *to define procedure for how dashboard managers will be assigned.*
Action: Catherine to initiate the process and communicate the timeline to impact the draft Monitor on launch in January.
 - (e) **Action:** Catherine to provide the results of the stakeholder survey with the final confirmed list to OpenAIRE and Zenodo on 10th November.
 - (f) **Action:** OpenAIRE to update the draft *National Open Access Report, Ireland* by 15th November and provide to Catherine for distribution.
 - (g) **Action:** OpenAIRE to prepare mockups of visualisations for what it would look like to (a) not identify green as “open access” without an open license and (b) identifying all green as “open access”, but distinguishing between green with open license and green without open license.
 - (h) **Action:** Advisory Group to give feedback on the OpenAIRE mockups and agree on how green will be represented in the Report and Monitor.
3. **OpenAIRE presentation of National Open Access Monitor, Ireland Report**
 4. **Advisory Group feedback on National Open Access Monitor, Ireland Report**
 5. **OpenAIRE presentation and demo of draft National Open Access Monitor, Ireland**
 6. **Advisory Group feedback on draft National Open Access Monitor, Ireland**